

**ЛИНГВОКОГНИТИВНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЕРБАЛИЗАЦИИ
КОНЦЕПТА «СТРАХ» В ЯЗЫКОВЫХ КАРТИНАХ РУССКОГО
И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЭТНОСА /**

**LINGUOCOGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF THE VERBALIZATION
OF THE CONCEPT OF "FEAR" IN THE LINGUISTIC REPRESENTATIONS
OF THE RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH ETHNOS**

Elena SIROTA, Associate Professor, PhD

(“Alecu Russo” Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

sirotaelena@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2662-8512>

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The process of changing the linguistic paradigm has led to the objectification of mental phenomena using the notion of “concept”, which has its own specifics in cognitive science and linguocultural studies. This is one aspect of the relevance of the study, the second is related to the need to correct this concept and clarify the means of its representation. The aim of the work is to analyze the objectification of the concept of “fear” in the linguistic worldviews of the Russian and English ethnicities. The work methodology is based on the conceptual principles of the aforementioned sciences. In the analysis of linguistic facts, various methods were used, including: same analysis, the method of dictionary definitions, etymological analysis, and field structuring. Results of the study: a definition of the concept of “fear” in Russian and English is given; based on the proposed definition, the concept is structured, and the core and periphery of the concept are identified. Comparing the specifics of the concept in two languages, we come to the conclusion that in both languages it is possible to identify both integral and differential semantic features of the specified concept.